

150°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 180°; *o*-chlorophenyl 185°; and *p*-chlorophenyl 197°. All the compounds in general gave the following ir bands: 1 480–1 540 (NH stretch), 1 640–1 680 (C=O with aromatic phenyl group) and 820–880 cm⁻¹ (C₃N₃ stretch).

The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*) and gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at the concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The same method was adopted for determining antiseptic activity using *Streptococcus ficalis*. The zone of inhibition of both the activities of the test solution was recorded.

Maximum zone of inhibition was obtained for the culture *S. aureus*, in the case of 2-morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenoxy-(*p*-chlorophenylurea)-*s*-triazine. In the culture *E. coli*, maximum zone of inhibition was obtained in case of 2-morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenoxy-(*o*-chlorophenylurea)-*s*-triazine. Maximum zone of inhibition with culture *S. ficalis* was obtained in case of 2-morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenoxy-(*o*-chlorophenylurea)-*s*-triazine.

For both *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, 1,3,7,9-tetrachloro-10-(acetyl-*o*-nitrophenylurea)phenothiazine exhibited maximum zone of inhibition. In case of *S. ficalis*, 1,3,7,9-tetrachloro-10-(acetyl-*m*-nitrophenylurea)phenothiazine exhibited maximum zone of inhibition.

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Chemical Investigation of *Salvia lanata* Roxb. and *Bignonia anguis Cati*

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IN previous communications¹⁻⁴, we reported the isolation and identification of some di- and tri-terpenes from the whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *Salvia lanata* Roxb.⁵. We now report

the isolation and characterisation of two more diterpenes from the benzene extract of *S. lanata* and the result of systematic chemical examination of *Bignonia anguis Cati*⁶ (Bignoniaceae) on which no phytochemical work seems to have been reported so far.

The concentrated benzene extract of the defatted whole plant of *S. lanata* was subjected to chromatographic analysis over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity. The later fraction of benzene eluate furnished a diterpene, C₂₀H₂₈O₃ (*M*⁺ 314), m.p. 165–68°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 210, 248, 330sh and 455 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350, 1 660 and 1 630 cm⁻¹ (*o*-hydroxy*parab*enzoquinone). On catalytic hydrogenation over Adam's catalyst followed by oxidation by air it formed a compound, C₂₀H₂₈O₃ (*M*⁺ 316), m.p. 178–80°, identical with royleanone (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc with authentic specimen⁷) and was characterised as 6-dehydroroyleanone⁷. Further elution of the column with benzene–chloroform (1 : 1) afforded a gummy residue which dissolved in solvent ether, extracted with 5% NaOH solution, acidified with cold dilute HCl and extracted with solvent ether. The concentrated ether extract was chromatographed over silica gel and the benzene eluate yielded a crystalline solid, C₂₀H₂₈O₃ (*M*⁺ 300), m.p. 290–92°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 230 and 280 nm (phenol); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (phenolic OH), 1 670 cm⁻¹ (conjugated ketone) and was characterised as sugiol⁸.

The air-dried powdered whole plant of *B. anguis Cati* was extracted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and methanol. The concentrated petroleum ether extract on chromatographic separation over silica gel gave a white solid, (*M*⁺ 410), m.p. 83–84°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 cm⁻¹ (associated OH) in petroleum ether eluate. The compound has been identified as octacosanol⁹ by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the authentic sample. The concentrated methanolic extract of the defatted whole plant was chromatographed over silica gel and the elution of the column with ethyl acetate furnished a light yellow solid crystallised from methanol, (*M*⁺ 450), m.p. 215–16°; ν_{max} 3 350 (OH), 1 670 (tetrasubstituted double bond) and 1 695 cm⁻¹ (conjugated C=C). The identity of this compound with tectol¹⁰ has been established by the usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the authentic sample of tectol. Further elution of the column with the same solvent afforded another solid, (*M*⁺ 302), m.p. 340°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 345 (bonded OH) and 1 730 cm⁻¹ (lactone). It was characterised as ellagic acid¹¹ through direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the authentic specimen.

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A New Anthraquinone Pigment from *Cassia mimosoides* Linn.†

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IN our previous communication¹ we reported the isolation of an anthraquinone pigment, m.p. 160–62°, from the aerial parts (leaves and stems) of *C. mimosoides* Linn.² In the present paper a structure for the above pigment is advanced on the basis of spectral evidence.

The air-dried powdered aerial parts of *C. mimosoides* were successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform. The concentrated chloroform extract of the defatted aerial parts was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene–chloroform (1:1) mixture afforded a yellow solid which was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow leaflets, C₁₆H₁₂O₅ (M⁺ 284), m.p. 160–62°; gave positive test with methanolic magnesium acetate for anthraquinone³ and was found to contain one methoxy group as indicated by Zeisel experiment; λ_{max} (EtOH) 257, 267, 275sh, 288, 390, 415 and 435 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 670 (non-chelated C=O), 1 640 (chelated C=O) and 1 675 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation);

δ 3.90 (3H, s, Ar-OMe). These data, in conjunction with the fact that the pigment gives a dimethyl ether (4) C₁₈H₁₆O₅ (M⁺ 322), m.p. 178–80°, on treatment with diazomethane, suggest that the compound is a 1,8-dihydroxyanthraquinone with one methoxy group^{4,5} like physcion (3).

The mass spectral analysis is also consistent with the above view. The mass fragmentation pattern of the pigment is typical of polysubstituted anthraquinone⁶ and showed significant peaks at m/z 285 (M⁺+1), 256, 228, 198, 197, 183, 181 and 180 besides the molecular ion peak at m/z 284. The ¹H nmr spectrum (90 MHz, CDCl₃) of the compound displayed signals at δ 2.35 (3H, s, aromatic C-methyl), 3.90 (3H, s, one aromatic methoxy), 6.70 (d, J 2Hz, C₇-H), 7.40 (d, J 2.5Hz C₂-H), 7.60 (d, J 9Hz, C₃-H) and 7.80 (d, J 9Hz, C₄-H) assignable to four aromatic protons. The spectrum is practically identical with that of physcion except for the appearance of two doublets of one proton each in the aromatic region at δ 7.60 (d, J 9Hz) and 7.80 (d, J 9Hz) attributable respectively to C₃-H and C₄-H instead of two singlets of one proton each at δ 7.17 and 7.74 for C₃-H and C₄-H in the spectrum of physcion⁷. All these spectral observations reveal that the pigment differs from physcion in the position of aromatic C-methyl and hence may be formulated as 1,8-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-2-methyl-anthraquinone (1).

- 1; R-R₂-R₃-H, R₁-CH₃,
- 2; R-R₂-R₁-CH₃, R₃-H
- 3; R-R₂-R₁-H, R₃-CH₃,
- 4; R-R₂-R₃-CH₃, R-H

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